

Spacetime vacuum and Spin Statistics

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Advanced quantum field theory is not entirely necessary in order to explain the Pauli Exclusion Principle, and hence spin–statistics. What is essential is entanglement structure, in the form of isotropic spin correlation. Reviewing a paper by O’Hara we summarize the result and point out the residual “mystery” of spin–statistics, and propose a natural explanation for the phenomenon using the framework of topological 4-geon theory (a gravitational theory of quantum mechanics).

We revisit two persistent interpretive problems in quantum theory: (i) the origin of fermionic exchange symmetry, as expressed in the spin–statistics connection and the Pauli exclusion principle, and (ii) the status of so-called “virtual particles” associated with internal lines of Feynman diagrams.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Is the essential feature of quantum mechanics (and quantum field theory) entanglement, and nothing but entanglement? [1] We can be appropriately agnostic on the answer while presenting a local realist framework for understanding why Schrödinger may have been more on-the-nose than he realized.

We revisit two persistent interpretive problems in quantum theory: (i) the origin of fermionic exchange symmetry, as expressed in the spin–statistics connection and the Pauli exclusion principle, and (ii) the status of so-called “virtual particles” associated with internal lines of Stückelberg–Feynman diagrams.

The first topic is treated in the language of spacetime algebra (STA), where spinors are taken not as material objects but as transformation instructions relating measurement frames and particle observables. In this setting we argue that a substantial part of the spin–statistics story can be formulated without invoking the full machinery of relativistic quantum field theory. Following and reformulating ideas due to O’Hara, and drawing on the geometric algebra treatment of multiparticle systems due to Doran, Lasenby and collaborators [2, 3], we review ideas of O’Hara [4–6] which isolate isotropic spin coupling as the essential structural ingredient behind antisymmetric two-fermion states and hence behind the Pauli principle.

The second topic concerns the widespread but misleading language of particles “borrowing energy” or “popping out of the vacuum.” We argue that, within the sum-over-histories and Lagrangian path-integral formulations, internal lines are better understood as bookkeeping devices in a perturbative expansion of stochastic correlation amplitudes, *not as virtual particles*, and not even as borrowed particles, but more akin to temporarily traded real

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particles.¹ On this view the appearance of off-shell propagation reflects the non-local and generically open-system character of a spacetime cobordism treated only through effective boundary data. This motivates a stochastic reading of quantum dynamics in which the relevant processes are non-Markovian and, in Barandes’ sense, indivisible [7, 8].

Combining our ideas with the latter framework of Barandes helps us explain why the path-integral formalism can be treated stochastically. The critical issue being that interference must be accounted for in the path integral, which therefore must be a sum over amplitudes, not a classical statistical mechanics. QM is decidedly non-classical — the main lesson from the EPRB experiments. The issue we address is how is QM non-classical? Is it a literal sum-over-histories ontology which the path integral formalism “reveals,” or is that level of description still merely statistical and book-keeping? (That is, not the hard cold reality of what goes on in the spacetime cobordism between measurements.) We cannot definitively answer this question, but we venture some ideas that give one the scope to favour the former stochastic view of the SOH or path-integral formalism. *This would be easy if it were not for interference!* Interference being a highly dynamic phenomenon, it is difficult to conceive of single-particle interference as merely statistical. Yet this is what we will propose (following Barandes [7]), but with an added twist which identifies the non-stochastic aspects of interference and entanglement.

Throughout the paper we use $Cl_{3,1}$ as the minimal geometric arena in which the exchange structure can be reasoned about. At the same time we argue that this is only a toy model for a more adequate algebraic setting. In particular, the complexified and doubled Clifford framework,

$$Cl_4 \cong \mathbb{C} \otimes Cl_{3,1}, \quad Cl_8 \cong Cl_{0,2} \otimes Cl_{4,4},$$

is proposed as the natural setting for intrinsic algebraic entanglement. In the topological 4-geon programme this extra structure is interpreted not as a merely formal complex phase, but as encoding an oscillatory wormhole degree of freedom. The claims made at this latter level are in order to reinterpret the established exchange algebra for fermions and bosons, while the topological interpretation is offered as a geometric proposal for what the formalism may be telling us.

Why do fermions exclude one another from the same one-particle state, while bosons do not? And what, if

anything, are we entitled to mean by the “virtual particles” attached to internal lines in perturbative quantum field theory? These are not unrelated curiosities. In both cases the underlying conceptual difficulties are the same: one mistakes a calculational representation for an ontology. In the first case antisymmetric multiparticle amplitudes are too quickly reified into a mysterious microscopic repulsion. In the second case perturbative propagator factors are too quickly reified into short-lived particles that somehow evade energy conservation. The aim of this paper is to (pun intended) disentangle formal results from loose-speaking physical interpretation in both settings, and to do so in a language that keeps the real spacetime geometry in view.

Our starting point is the spacetime algebra $Cl_{3,1}$, used here in its role as a geometric reformulation of relativistic spinor theory. In this language a spinor is most naturally read as an even-grade multivector encoding a transformation between frames or measurement descriptions, rather than as a little material object inhabiting spacetime. This distinction is conceptually useful in the present context, because the spin–statistics connection concerns not the “substance” of a fermion but the symmetry properties of the amplitudes or spinorial descriptors used to represent possible outcomes. The algebra makes that distinction helpfully transparent, and it also allows one to formulate two-particle exchange structure without immediately appealing to the full field operator formalism.

For the first half of the paper we ask how much of the phenomenon can already be understood from the geometry of two-particle spin states, rotational covariance, and the structure of exchange in the STA multiparticle formalism? The guiding idea, following O’Hara [5], is that isotropic spin coupling is the relevant physical condition. In modern language one would say that the relevant states are rotationally invariant entangled pairs. The claim is that while entanglement accompanies fermionic statistics, it is the additional rotational symmetry of isotropic spin coupling which organizes the antisymmetric sector in a way that makes the Pauli principle far less mysterious than it appears when stated only as an axiom about anti-commuting field operators. Due to the seemingly limited recognition of these nuances in the general physics community this paper is pedagogical as much as technical: we want to display the exchange structure in the clearest available geometric terms.

This pedagogical goal also explains a limitation of the paper. The algebra $Cl_{3,1}$ is sufficient to exhibit the exchange geometry, the rotor action, and the relation between singlet structure and antisymmetry. But we shall argue that it is not the final arena in which the ontology should be sought. As a toy model, STA is excellent; but as a complete account of entanglement, it is too lean.

Supporting this work is the thesis of Imahori [9] which shows the complexified Clifford algebras are a, “foundation of our geometrical description of quantum states,” and that the Clifford algebra is thus a natural *algebraic*

¹ As should become evident, there is some flexibility in how we apply these monetary analogies to the internal lines. The key idea we would like to promote is that Nature is not operating like a credit-banking system (in the metaphor, that is, using money you do not “have” but are given and need to pay-back). Why not? Because we stipulate the conservation laws hold exactly. Thus the situation with virtual particles is better thought of as a trading analogy.

underpinning² for EPR entanglement. Imahori helpfully establishes a, “natural correspondence between the two formulations of quantum mechanics, namely, the state vector formulation and the density operator formulation.” This is work we thus do not need to reproduce, but is part & parcel of our program. We regard that work as half of our program. Our goal is to uncover real spacetime topology as the foundation of the applicability of complexified $Cl_{p,q}$ as the minimalist renditions of the notion of ‘quantum state.’

I.A. Entanglement and Spacetime Algebra

Our working conjecture is that genuinely intrinsic entanglement structure is possible only after a doubling of the spacetime frame. In that sense the passage from $Cl_{3,1}$ to a doubled complexified Clifford setting is a structural enlargement. Without this enlargement single-particle entanglement would still be mysterious and metaphysical, at least if one were to adopt a minimalist framework of 4D spacetime. Our working conjecture includes such minimalism.

We do not claim 4D spacetime minimalism is all we need for physics. What we argue is just what can be purchased from such minimalism? Can we purchase “everything”? (Everything that is physical.)

Regarding Pauli Exclusion as ‘in the package of everything’: It is easy enough to describe spin–statistics in terms of multi-particle QM, using the natural tensor structure for coupled systems. This is inadequate for a single particle.

Why is this important? The answer is because a single particle cannot exhibit self-interference if it is not entangled with itself. Hence entanglement cannot be just a phenomena involving only Bell pairs (the spacetime bipartite tensor structure). Single fermions (and bosons) must also be self-entangled. Thus in the context of spacetime physics (or our topological 4-geon theory (T4G) ideas [10, 11]) we must up-grade to a doubled STA Clifford algebra like Cl_8 . When fermions are represented by the transformation instructions in the Cl_8 even subalgebra, we have a bipartite STA structure, but no “bridge” relating them. It is “all algebra, no geometry.” To get the geometry correct we find we need to complexify this algebra. Although it is only a type of heuristic, we have been thinking of the complex phase structure this adds as a primitive algebraic accounting for wormhole bridges. We mean literal wormholes, not merely EPR correlation on some putative undefined de Sitter CFT boundary. Our T4G wormholes are fairly local, they are mostly in the interior of any given spacetime cobordism between two times t_1 and t_2 defining a “measurement” boundary (set-up and measurement, whether weak or strong measurement). Though one never really knows where one end

of a T4G wormhole could be, hence the QM description has to be stochastic. (Any time entanglement structure is important, the cobordism development must be statistical.)

Weak measurements [12] are not of the cobordism interior in this view, they redefine the boundary t_2 at the point of the weak measurement. All that weak measurements do is give you less data, they are not “probing the cobordism interior.” See also [13, 14].

We treat $Cl_4 \cong \mathbb{C} \otimes Cl_{3,1}$ as an intermediate shadow of a richer framework, and regard Cl_8 as the more natural home for algebraic self-entanglement. One can write down a Witt basis (ladder operators, or *null basis*) in Cl_4 , but this is not a 4D spacetime, since a Witt basis of *index* n requires $2n$ orthonormal basis vectors to be defined in conventional Lorentzian/Riemann coordinates. The Null space is not the Vector space. The Witt basis with n null pairs lives on an underlying orthogonal space of dimension $2n$ [15]. Thus Cl_4 is the Clifford algebra of a 4-dimensional complex orthogonal space, whose Witt index is 2.³ Thus Cl_4 when complexified admits a Witt basis of only two null pairs, not four, hence too few for the Standard Model fermions.

The stronger topological reading of this doubling, in which the complex phase is interpreted as an oscillatory wormhole degree of freedom in an ER=EPR-inspired 4-geon picture, is speculative; however, it provides a concrete research programme rather than a merely verbal metaphor.

I.B. Spacetime Vacuum and Cobordism Interiors

The second half of the paper turns to a different but related quantum mythology: the claim that virtual particles “borrow energy” for a short time. The phrase is pedagogically catchy but technically misleading. Energy–time uncertainty is not a licence for violations of conservation laws, and internal lines in Feynman graphs are not accounted for because of actual existence of transient particles. In the path-integral formulation they arise from the perturbative organization of amplitudes, that is, from the decomposition of a global sum over histories into diagrammatic contributions.

It is an extra prejudice or presumption to suppose the ‘quantum fields’ can fluctuate to produce these processes ‘out of nothing.’ In a *quantum field ontology* this would be reasonable, but we have been unable to motivate such an ontology, because in our entire research program the spinor fields are not physical, they’re stochastic descriptors — transformation instructions. How does a transformation instruction “pop up” out of spacetime vacuum

² The ‘underpin’ notion is a deliberate pun, see §III.B.

³ A standard quadratic-forms reference for the abstract Witt-index statement: a nonsingular quadratic space of dimension $2n$ is hyperbolic iff it contains a totally isotropic subspace of dimension n , and the Witt index is the maximal possible dimension of such a subspace [16].

fluctuations? The question makes no sense in our topological 4-geon framework, since it is a category error.

The “virtual” off-shell character is a necessity arising from the *possibility* of such topology changing events in spacetime, which therefore need to be accounted for but they should not be regarded as episodes in which nature suspends exact conservation. Our view is that we should try to determine how these events occur, without violating conservation laws (which ultimately should be topological and inviolable, if they are elementary).

This is especially clear when one regards the relevant spacetime region as a cobordism specified by boundary data. Generically such a region is not truly closed, and the effective dynamics seen at the boundary is therefore stochastic and coarse-grained. We do *not*, however, conclude from this that the internal structures appearing in perturbation theory are merely fictitious bookkeeping devices. Our claim is more subtle. The standard language of “virtual particles popping out of the vacuum” is, in our view, physically misleading; but the topology-changing processes depicted by Stückelberg–Feynman vertices may nonetheless correspond to real processes in the open cobordism. What fails is not conservation law, but the assumption that the special-relativistic subsystem under study is dynamically closed. In the presence of wormhole or entanglement structure, degrees of freedom may enter or leave the cobordism in a manner invisible to a purely local description. Perturbative internal lines are then to be read neither as literal temporary particles created *ex nihilo*, nor as empty formal artifacts, but as amplitude level signatures of genuine nonlocal exchange with the larger spacetime system.

In our view the latter statement is the better more physically meaningful expression of the concept of a dynamical spacetime vacuum:— that is, the generic spacetime cobordism region defined by “an experiment” is not closed and not isolated, and is quantum mechanically *acausal* (admits effects from T4G wormholes, or *nearly* closed timelike curves).

This perspective also suggests a common origin for interference phenomena. The same nontrivial entanglement structure that, in our view, underlies isotropic spin-coupling and hence Pauli exclusion, may also underlie the interference patterns ordinarily attributed to superposition alone. In the topological picture motivating this paper, wormhole-entanglement oscillations provide the physical mechanism, while the usual quantum amplitudes provide their effective boundary description.

The suggestive point, for us, is that the same refusal to reify the intermediate bookkeeping appears in both topics: neither antisymmetric exchange amplitudes nor internal propagator factors should be mistaken for little ontological actors. On the other hand, we feel the real physics is more subtle, and that topology changing processes depicted in Stückelberg–Feynman diagrams do depict actual topology changing events that do occur in the spacetime cobordism. Ascertaining (or just theorizing) how they may occur without violating conservation

laws is our main interest.

The internal line is taken to correspond to a real intermediate topological process, though not necessarily to a freely propagating on-shell particle localized within the subsystem. (Unless it is on-shell, but generically the internal lines will be off-shell.)

It also prepares the ground for the topological 4-geon interpretation, where the failure of naïve subsystem closure is not a nuisance but a feature, needed to explain the loose language of “virtual particles” in more precise terms, and without referring to any virtuality.

Quantum theory, on the topological 4-geon view pursued here, is fundamentally a theory of constrained stochastic amplitudes on spacetime processes rather than a mechanics of persisting microscopic objects with fully determinate intermediate histories. In that sense it is natural to compare the sum-over-histories (SOH) framework with non-Markovian and indivisible stochastic dynamics (ISQM) — these two approaches to QM/QFT are not so incompatible as one might presuppose, and can be seen as looking at the same ontology from two different modelling points of view. The SOH *pretends* all paths occur, but only computes a weighted Lagrangian sum allowing for interference, hence admits maybe not all paths literally do occur, while the ISQM posits the same, all paths or interactions *could* occur but merely non-Markov stochastically.

Put in starker terms, from one measurement on one particle, one cannot detect any interference at all, not ever. Yet there must have been interference.

We do not claim here to derive quantum theory from such a stochastic model, we will appeal to previous preprints for sketches of how to do so [10, 11]. The more limited claim in this paper is that this language helps to state cleanly what perturbation theory is doing, and why internal lines can be read almost literally, but not without a new theoretical justification, which we hope to provide.

The paper is organized as follows. In Section II we set up the STA description of one- and two-particle systems, review the role of rotors and multiparticle correlators, and restate the exchange problem in geometric terms. Section II.B reformulates the O’Hara programme in this language, emphasizing isotropic spin coupling as the structural condition behind antisymmetry and Pauli exclusion. Section II.A explains why $C\ell_{3,1}$ should be regarded as only a toy model, and sketches the case for a doubled complex Clifford framework in which entanglement is intrinsic to the algebraic architecture.

In section II.D we provide a speculative (cartoon, or picturesque) account in terms of spacetime geometry for Pauli exclusion (PEP) and boson condensates. This account will be based on the equally speculative ideas of topological 4-geon theory (T4G), which is a gravitational explanation of quantum mechanics [17, 18].

Section III will examine internal lines in perturbation theory and the path integral, arguing against the “borrowed energy” mythology and in favour of an open cobor-

dism reading. Finally, Section IV gathers the formal and speculative threads together and states the open problems for a future topological account.

We think on roughly two levels throughout this paper. On the first level, which is meant to be mathematically conservative, we review and reorganize known exchange structure in a geometric algebra idiom. On the second level, which is explicitly conjectural, we ask what sort of spacetime topology could make that formal structure intelligible. The first level is intended to stand on its own. The second is offered as a proposal for further work.

Much of the strangeness of quantum spin–statistics can be explained to students without the esoterica of relativistic quantum field theory. But in any case, QFT is a stochastic theory of non-Markov stochastic dynamics. This is why fermionic symmetry (anti-symmetry upon exchange) is a statistical result — it is because the spinors describing fermions are already mathematical model objects at a statistical level of description. In section II we expand upon these claims, using the Clifford algebra formulation of quantum mechanics as the simplest language available. This does not go beyond anything in orthodox QM, but it does set the scene for a more non-standard comprehension of fermion statistics.

II. SPIN STATISTICS

We begin this section with a quick review of Clifford algebra Standard Models. The main result to highlight is the need to upgrade from the 4D Minkowski topology of the STA (the $\mathcal{Cl}_{3,1}$ algebra which is suitable for Dirac Theory) to a complexified \mathcal{Cl}_8 . This doubles the spacetime frame, but is still an algebraic particle model in strictly 4D spacetime. We interpret this need as theoretical evidence for wormhole bridges at the Planck scale. This is only an interpretation, and can be *forced* only by *presuming* there is nothing to work with other than Einstein’s 4D spacetime. This is a type of minimalism, a self-imposed theoreticians constraint, similar to the stance adopted by Turok & Boyle and colleagues. [19, 20].

II.A. Clifford algebras for QM

This section is supplementary for this paper, but we wish to lead with it because it should help cement one of the main unifying concepts in our T4G research program, which is that the spinors of QM and QFT are not direct representations of the elementary particles, and are instead transformation instructions which describe and define the possible topological transforms which the elementary particles can suffer.

There are two useful levels for this point of view, first the 4D spacetime algebra, which although a toy model, helps to highlight that at least in Dirac Theory, the spinors are nothing but transformation instructions, not ontology. The second level is the full Standard Model

algebra, which in our view is minimally \mathcal{Cl}_8 (subject to future collider physics findings).

II.A.1. The STA View

In the Spacetime algebra $\mathcal{Cl}_{3,1}$ the Dirac spinors are fully represented by the even subalgebra, there is a direct isomorphism between the matrix Hilbert space and the algebra $\mathcal{Cl}_{3,1}^+$, which we will now review.

The matrix representations require a basis choice. There are three commonly used,

1. Dirac basis.
2. Weyl representation.
3. Majorana.

The Majorana spinors are all real-valued and the Dirac matrices are ‘imaginary’. The particle (represented *merely* by its transformation instruction!) is then its own antiparticle. That’s useful for neutrinos (also the photon).

The Dirac basis is the one we are going to use next. It naturally splits into space rotations and Lorentz boosts (not directly particle/antiparticle). Each pair are made from two Pauli spinors, ϕ, η , by

$$\psi = \phi + \eta\sigma_3.$$

In the STA the bivector $\gamma_{12} = I\sigma_3$, plays the precise role of the unit imaginary i in the orthodox textbook matrix Hilbert representation. (The textbooks are *bad*, since they confuse *distinct* more geometrically meaningful unit imaginaries.)

We use $\mathcal{Cl}_{3,1}$ so we tend to need $I = \gamma_1\gamma_2\gamma_3\gamma_0$, to agree with Hestenes–Lasenby–Doran who use $\mathcal{Cl}_{1,3}$ and $I = \gamma_0\gamma_1\gamma_2\gamma_3$. But invariably we get a \pm sign wrong on occasion, which is a disaster. It really is! It keeps me awake at night. All things change if you let $-1 = +1$.

The Weyl representation changes basis so the spinor components are sorted into left and right chirality,

$$\psi = \psi_L + \psi_R.$$

These can be obtained by applying a unitary transform to the Dirac spinor (in the matrix algebra).

As a warm-up to the Dirac spinors, one can check the Pauli matrix algebra is the same (up to isomorphism) as the algebra for the Clifford,

$$\sigma_k = \gamma_k\gamma_0.$$

No imaginary numbers needed. These are all the generators of boosts in 4D spacetime, via rotors $R = e^{\alpha\sigma_k}$.

The Clifford Pauli algebra \mathcal{Cl}_3^+ of the *relative vectors* (bivectors) $\sigma_k = \gamma_k\gamma_0$ is exactly isomorphic to the Pauli matrix algebra.

We define a generic (mixed) Dirac spinor via two Pauli spinors,

$$\psi = \phi + \eta\sigma_3$$

The mapping from-to matrix Hilbert space is then,

$$\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{M}) \ni |\psi\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} a^0 + ia^3 \\ -a^2 + ia^1 \\ -b^3 + ib^0 \\ -b^1 - ib^2 \end{pmatrix} \longleftrightarrow \quad (1)$$

$$\psi_{\text{Dirac}} = a^0 + Ia^k\sigma_k + I(b^0 + b^k I\sigma_k) \in C\ell_{1,3}^+$$

The commutation relations for the $\sigma_i\sigma_3$ are here what permute around the $\pm b_k$ relative to the a_k . For example, $\sigma_1\sigma_2 = I\sigma_3$, $\sigma_2\sigma_3 = -I\sigma_1$, $\sigma_3\sigma_1 = I\sigma_2$.

Using the shorthand for the mapping with a pair of Pauli spinors $|\phi\rangle$ and $|\eta\rangle$, for which the real geometric $I\sigma_3$ represents the unit imaginary i in Pauli QM, then:

$$\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{M}) \ni |\psi\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} |\phi\rangle \\ |\eta\rangle \end{pmatrix} \mapsto \psi = \phi + \eta\sigma_3 \in C\ell_{1,3}^+$$

All fine and good, but what we really would like to emphasize is a density–polar form of the spinor:

$$\psi = \sqrt{\rho} e^{I\beta} R \quad (2)$$

This is what is more important to highlight. The previous isomorphism (1) is a purely mathematical notion, we lay out the correspondence just for satisfying field theorists that we have their objects and symmetries all wrapped inside the STA.

In this density–polar form, ρ is a real probability density, and thus carries most of the statistical information for a transformation. I is the spacetime pseudoscalar, and so the fact $e^{I\beta}$ is a pure duality transform, it permits transforms that mix fermion and anti-fermion. The lastly factor, which uses up all the Dirac degrees of freedom, is the rotor, which can be a combination of space rotations with boosts.

Hence our main conclusion, reached long ago by David Hestenes [21], which is that the spinors are not models for particles. They are models for transformations of our imposed Clifford frames $\{\gamma^\mu\}$. No proof is needed for this interpretation, since it follows as definition from the Clifford frames. The STA frame we impose is our laboratory construct, it is unphysical. The physics content is in using the spinor to transform our frame to that of the elementary particle.

Then when we gauge the equation for these transformations, we are permitting further transformations that model the elementary particle interactions.

The quantum theory is thus not a theory of equations of motion. It is a theory of equations for transformations. This better suits a Lagrangian formulation. The time evolution of the spinors is a time evolution of transformations that are applicable for a stochastic description of a spacetime cobordism region. When we time evolve

a spinor directly, as in the Dirac Theory, we can fool ourselves into thinking the object we time evolve is an ‘element of reality,’ whereas the STA point of view above can help disabuse us of such fanciful notions. We are dealing with a theory of *Equations for Transformations*. This is a huge part of the reason why QM and QFT can seem so strange compared to classical mechanics. It is not so strange once you appreciate the “equations of motion” are not longer equations of motion. They are *equations for transformation instructions*. That’s an abstraction layer above classical mechanics. It is thus no good to think of a transition from QM to CM. The two are different frameworks entirely.

Although we will not define it here, our contention elsewhere would be that there is no longer any such thing as classical mechanics. Everything is quantum mechanical, nothing is ever truly in superposition, but the transformation instructions need to be put into *statistical* superposition!- — for the exact sorts of reason we will discuss in the rest of this paper. (Entanglement and interference reasons.)

II.A.2. The $\mathcal{C}\ell_8$ View

We will not need the entire Standard Model for this paper. All we would like to point out in this section is that we cannot yet find the full Standard Model in just the STA, but by doubling and complexifying the algebra we find all the symmetries of the LR-CPT-symmetric Standard Model, see [11] and also see [22] (required reading).

The note we wish to make here is just that we have a spacetime topology justification for the doubling and complexification, which is that the extra tensor structure is the signature — in the algebra — of wormhole topology. It cannot hardly be anything else if we impose the minimalism of 4D spacetime as all we are allowed to work with.

This is just a conjecture, but the idea is that the following three “bridge” structures are intimately related, and in 4D spacetime one cannot *reasonably* have any one of these without the other two:

1. ER-bridges — these provide the generic 4D spacetime cobordism with stochastic indivisibility.[7]
2. EPR-bridges — necessary for the EPR correlations to be local and real. [23].
3. \mathbb{C} -bridges — these are algebraic, and are necessary in $\mathcal{C}\ell_8$ for phase oscillations between two STA frames. These are necessary in order to fully model the Standard Model of elementary particles coupled to the gravity vierbein (12 bosons, 48 fermions, and 72 dimension zero scalars).[22, 24]

The conjectured connection is pretty obvious: in 4D spacetime there is no candidate for an EPR bridge *other* than an ER-bridge. Unless we admit mysticism and fibre bundles, which violates our self-imposed constraint of

minimalism.⁴ Moreover, the path-integral for the Standard Model must have entanglement to have interference, and this requires an algebraic bridge between the doubled STA frames in \mathcal{Cl}_8 .

To be explicit, note that the doubled STA frame is an algebraic account of bipartite wormhole topology. Yet again, one can debate the ontology, and that's fine, but we are going with the hypothesis the ontology is wormhole structure at the Planck scale — the only scale for which wormholes are viably stable.[25, 26]

What we will see in the following sections is that because spinors for fermions are valued in the *even* subalgebra (for either $\mathcal{Cl}_{3,1}$ or the more complete $\mathbb{C}\ell_8$), they are naturally anti-symmetric forms. This implies the Fermi-Dirac statistics.

II.A.3. Multi-fermion systems

In the STA $\mathcal{Cl}_{3,1}$ the Pauli matrices have a pure spacetime multivector representation, and are nothing but the relative bivectors — that is, they are like 1-vectors, but only with respect to a designated timelike basis orientation = γ_0 , otherwise they are proper bivectors in those frames and generators of boosts, as previously noted. One may think of γ_0 as the particle current direction in a local reference frame co-moving with the particles, hence this is physical and does not break Lorentz invariance. The Pauli bivectors are defined by the geometric product,

$$\sigma_k = \gamma_k \gamma_0.$$

and for an orthonormal frame $\gamma_k \gamma_0 = \gamma_k \wedge \gamma_0$. We always presume to be using an orthonormal frame.

To adequately describe spin-coupled systems — which is critical for a purely geometric account of Pauli Exclusion — we introduce two-particle system symbolism as follows. There are two STA frames, one for each particle. The particle with label “1” has Pauli bivectors,

$$\overset{1}{i}\sigma_k, \quad k \in 1,2,3$$

Where $\overset{j}{i}$ is the spacetime pseudoscalar for the j Clifford frame, often denoted

$$I = \sigma_1 \sigma_2 \sigma_3.$$

when the frame is generic. The left-superscript label $\overset{j}{i}$ applies to both I and σ_k .

It is convenient that entanglement is monogamous, because this means for the remainder of this paper we will only need the above clumsy notation for two-fermion coupled systems.

II.B. Spin coupling, exchange, and the Pauli principle

We begin with the spacetime-algebra description of two indistinguishable fermionic degrees of freedom, following the multiparticle STA formalism of Doran, Lasenby, and collaborators, together with the *isotropic spin-coupling* criterion emphasized by O'Hara. Our aim in this section is modest but precise: to isolate the minimal geometric structure needed to recover antisymmetric exchange and hence the Pauli exclusion principle for the class of states of interest.

Proposition 1 (Two-particle correlator and common complex structure). *Let the two-particle STA be generated by two commuting copies of the single-particle spacetime algebra, with correlator*

$$E = \frac{1}{2}(1 - \overset{1}{J} \overset{2}{J}),$$

where each $\overset{k}{J}$ squares to -1 . Then E is idempotent and defines a common effective imaginary unit

$$J = E \overset{1}{J} = E \overset{2}{J} = \frac{1}{2}(\overset{1}{J} + \overset{2}{J}), \quad J^2 = -E,$$

thereby reducing the doubled spinor description to a properly correlated two-particle state space.

The significance of this construction is that it gives a coordinate-free description of the two-particle spinor space in which rotational covariance and exchange may be studied geometrically rather than component-wise.

Proposition 2 (Isotropic spin-coupling and the singlet sector). *The rotationally invariant two-particle spin singlet is represented in the correlated STA by*

$$\varpi = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\overset{1}{i}\sigma_2 - \overset{2}{i}\sigma_2) E,$$

up to notational convention for the two particle labels. This state is distinguished by isotropic spin-coupling, and hence by invariance under common spatial rotations of the pair.

At this stage the formal point is still purely kinematical: isotropic spin-coupling picks out a geometrically preferred entangled sector.

Lemma 3 (Exchange antisymmetry from isotropic spin-coupling). *For indistinguishable particles prepared in the isotropically spin-coupled singlet sector, the exchange of particle labels induces antisymmetry of the two-particle amplitude,*

$$\psi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) = -\psi(\lambda_2, \lambda_1).$$

Consequently the coincident-state amplitude vanishes,

$$\psi(\lambda, \lambda) = 0,$$

which is the Pauli exclusion property.

⁴ It is certainly ok to go ahead and violate minimalism, but that is not our parsimonious research program.

This is the point at which O’Hara’s argument and the STA formalism meet. For the class of states governed by isotropic spin-coupling, the antisymmetric exchange structure is already visible in the geometry of the correlated two-particle spinor space.

Conjecture 1 (Topological interpretation). *The isotropically spin-coupled sector corresponds physically to a wormhole- or ER-bridge-mediated entanglement structure, and the exchange sign is the boundary amplitude shadow of a non-trivial topological process in spacetime.*

Note 1. Note that ${}^1\gamma_\mu$ and ${}^2\gamma_\mu$ are two full-blown copies of the entire spacetime algebra (STA). Which might strike some older sensitive folks as a bit profligate. But fear not! For a few reasons:

1. In general relativity we are already comfortable with the notion of a privileged local frame of reference that any particle essentially “carries around with itself.” A muon “knows” what its lifetime to decay is supposed to be, and it never changes, and a photon knows it’s supposed to “live & die in an instant” from source to sink. We are not making a copy of spacetime. The reference frames ${}^i\gamma_\mu$ are book-keeping accountancy, they’re not ontological.
2. But they do help us express a real physical relationship, in some cases (namely the cases where we entangle two geons).
3. Multi-particle quantum mechanics is an interesting applied field of research, but we’ll have very little use for it, because the case of a pair of indistinguishable particles is the only fundamental case we need consider, since, as we’ve learned, spin-coupled states can only exist in pairs. The exotic cases of GHZ states (multipartite entanglement) are a speciality topic, but pretty rare in the wild, and we’ll have a pretty similar STA generalization to handle them, if and when we bother to handle them.

Note 2. Crucially though, this is more than notation — since what we mean in T4G theory by these coupled pair systems is that an EPR=ER wormhole bridge might connect the two indistinguishable geons. If two fermions are not so coupled then we cannot write a pure singlet state to describe them, we’d have a mixed state. In T4G and in O’Hara’s terms, that just means the uncoupled geons are statistically independent, not Bell pairs. If they once had an ER bridge connecting them, it’s collapsed — by some ant or speck of dust or Dextor in his lab “making a measurement.”

Why is this T4G view justified?

It is because with an ER=EPR wormhole the same quantum information goes down both wormholes, or can traverse out either end, after perhaps oscillating in-between them a countable number of times.

Recall (or learn) that ‘wormholes growing’ means more information going in, an increase in the quantum complexity [27]. But fundamental particles do not grow in complexity, so their wormhole’s do not grow (a proper mathematical physics result! Go on, try to fact-check me!) and so the horizon of a minimal wormhole in a t4g-geon structure preserves quantum information until it decays, and so both ends of these Planckian wormholes in T4G theory have to be horizons for the same information, meaning they’re “the same particle” or two copies — coupled — of indistinguishable geon’s.

We realise this raises the conundrum that if 4-geons themselves contain CTC’s, then every fundamental particle modelled by a 4-geon has, in some sense, this sort of dual horizon, it “carries information about itself in duplicate,” is how we would put it. But we are not sure this gives us any headaches, in fact it greatly relieves one headache, which is how we can justify geometric amplitudes in the superpositions. We’re going to get an answer from entanglement in §III.B.

We now will proceed to justify the above propositions. We follow the approach of Lasenby & Doran’s section 9.4 in [28], and add only some minor rhetorical flourishes that encourage a topological 4-geon reading (which is not obligatory).

II.B.1. Two-particle Correlator

We have a copy of the pseudoscalar for each 4-geon, that is, for the space labelled by 1 there is a pseudoscalar 1i , and for the space labelled by 2 there is a pseudoscalar 2i . So we ought to write:

$${}^1J = {}^1i {}^1\sigma_3$$

or just,

$${}^1J = {}^1i\sigma_3$$

and likewise for 2J , 2i and ${}^2\sigma_3$. This is for notational convenience, to avoid a bit of mess down the road.

For either a coupled or uncoupled two-geon system with two-states, e.g., spin \uparrow and \downarrow we have the shorthand tensor product notation that covers the basis,

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

The first of these is also written $|++\rangle$ in bra-ket notation, the second $|+-\rangle$ and so forth. But we have a dictionary for translating these into geometric algebra spinors, ψ , or even elements of the Pauli \mathcal{G}_3^+ algebra.

For a two-geon system we will have a product spinor,

$${}^{12}\psi = {}^1\psi {}^2\psi$$

To be lazy we will refer to this two-fermion spinor as “ ψ ” for just this section of the paper.

We need the two-particle state to act on (or be acted upon) the multivectors in each of the product spaces in an invariant manner, so the 1J and 2J simply cannot be the pseudoscalar for the two-particle system. We need to find a new pseudoscalar that acts invariantly on both spaces when multiplying ψ .

$$\psi {}^1J = \psi {}^2J$$

And yet, taking note, each spinor in it's own half of the tensor space is just a normal Pauli rotor. So the above constraint is very interesting. But we are doing QM in T4G & GA context⁵ here, and so the spinors are not physical particles, they are not *the geons*. They are representative of processes or instructions for how to translate laboratory instrument settings onto the frame that describes the 4-geon properties, which is what a measurement theory demands, as per our previous philosophy and theory of QM from a T4G perspective.

That is all just to say that we are free to do essentially what we please to the separate spinors ${}^1\psi$ and ${}^2\psi$ provided we do not deform their action on their local variables in their respective k frames. This is another constraint on the possible form that the ${}^k\psi$ can take.

One shortcut through the potential mess is a slick but simple bit of algebra, just note that each kJ satisfies,

$$({}^kJ)^2 = -1,$$

so that,

$$\psi = -\psi {}^1J {}^2J$$

so we can form 2ψ by adding that expression to ψ , hence,

$$\begin{aligned} 2\psi &= \psi - \psi {}^1J {}^2J \\ \therefore \psi &= \frac{1}{2}\psi (1 - {}^1J {}^2J) \end{aligned}$$

and so in what seems like a bit of wizardly sleight of hand we've found a candidate form for the general two-particle state, which is that whatever $\psi = {}^1\psi {}^2\psi$ is, if it has this post-factor on the right-hand side it will have invariance upon right multiplications by the Pauli algebra mapping of the unit imaginary for both spaces in the tensor form (namely 1J and 2J). So, abstractly,

$$\psi = (\text{some spinors}) (1 - {}^1J {}^2J)$$

and we tidy this up a little by defining a new idempotent element we name, E ,

$$E = \frac{1}{2} (1 - {}^1J {}^2J)$$

since we need the factor of $1/2$ to make it square to itself, you can check that,

$$E^2 = E$$

which is the definition of an *idempotent* element of any algebra. (I do not know who settled on the name ' E ' for this idempotent, but it is kind of 'elementary.'). This property also means E is a *projector*. (You act with it once, it gives you back a new spinor projected onto a measurement subspace, but act twice it does no more or less.)

Next, with this projector defined we can now write down an invariant unit imaginary for the whole product space,

$$J = E {}^1J = E \langle J2 \rangle = \frac{1}{2} ({}^1J + {}^2J)$$

Again, you could scribble around a while trying to invent this, but you'll find it's the simplest and obvious choice. But you should check it is a tensor space version of the pseudoscalar:

$$J^2 = -1.$$

Which is not hard, since we already have $E^2 = E$, and $({}^kJ)^2 = -1$ for each geon's tensor space label ${}^k \in \{1, 2\}$.

You might be asking why we're doing all this? It is because we need a geometric algebra basis for this new thing called a 2-geon system. And that in turn is because later on we will want to couple such a system with a wormhole ER=EPR bridge, the same way we did last chapter.

The object that allows us to do this for geometric algebra spinors is this thing E , which we will now enshrine a bit further by christening it:

The object E generalizes to a system of n geons, where it is denoted E_n and is called *the quantum correlator*.

To figure out what E_n boils down to you need to have it satisfy:

$$E_n {}^iJ = E_n {}^kJ = J_n, \quad \text{for each } i, k \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$$

It turns out this is just a product over all the correlators with any one of the i , so we can choose ${}^i = 1$, for simplicity and write,

$$E_n = \prod_k^n \frac{1}{2} (1 - {}^1J {}^kJ).$$

Note also that we get the "complex structure" for the mapping from Hilbert to $C\ell_3^+$ space with any one of the iJ , so for instance,

$$J_n = E_n {}^kJ$$

is independent of which k label we choose, all give the same J_n .

The pay-off for going to all this effort is that now all the operations we did in the single 4-geon geometric algebra $C\ell_3^+$ work the same in the multi-particle setting, just with J_n instead of the old single GA pseudoscalar I .

So, reversion, space conjugate, Hermitian conjugate, Hermitian transpose, spinor inner product, grade projection $\langle \cdot \rangle$ all work the same as before. In particular rotations by rotors works the same.

⁵ Geometric algebra.

II.B.2. Notation for the 2-4geon systems

Suppose we had a two-4geon spinor expressed in geometric algebra of Cl_3 two-4geon space, that was something like,

$${}^{12}\psi = \cos(\alpha) {}^1i\sigma_2 + \sin(\alpha) {}^2i\sigma_2 E.$$

Note the nice convention to tidy this up a little, which is that when the pseudoscalar i is next to a ${}^i\sigma_k$ from one of the spaces of relative vectors we can drop the left script label on it, taking it as implied.

The good thing is, for our present purposes, we never need to worry about n particle states for $n > 2$ because the only phenomena that is intrinsically quantum mechanical is entanglement, and entanglement is monogamous, so ${}^{12}\psi$ should be as complicated as we wish to worry about. Fermionic $n \geq 3$ quantum mechanics is better served up in the Lagrangian path-integral formalism, which does away with explicit computations in these Fock spaces.

This is also really at the heart of the Pauli Exclusion Principle, as O'Hara shows, we need only be concerned with isotropic spin correlations or isotropic spin-coupling (ISC). This is restricted to two-particles. It *is* entanglement.

II.B.3. The coupled-geon basis states

Above we wrote down the Pauli column vector and ket representations for the basis states for a two-state 4geon system.⁶ That is, two maybe coupled (or maybe not coupled) geons, that have \uparrow and \downarrow states they can be projected into by a spin measurement.

It turns out we can get the tensored basis state just with geometric products of the correlator E and the ${}^1i\sigma_k$ and ${}^2i\sigma_k$

To do so, remember the principle mapping from $\mathcal{H} \mapsto Cl_3^+$:

$$\mathcal{H} \ni |\psi\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} a^0 + ia^3 \\ -a^2 + ia^1 \end{pmatrix} \mapsto \sqrt{\rho}R = a^0 + Ia^k \sigma_k \in Cl_3^+$$

From which we can read off the first basis column vector, which goes like,

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \mapsto 1$$

So in the 2-geon (potentially coupled, but maybe not) system we need to post-multiply by the correlator E_2 , so we've got,

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \mapsto (1)(1)E = E.$$

The other three 2-geon basis states are as follows. The second of the 1-geon base states goes as,

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \mapsto -a^2 I \sigma_2 = i \sigma_2 \quad (3)$$

so the second of the 2-geon base states must go as,

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \mapsto (1)(-{}^2i\sigma_2)E = -{}^2i\sigma_2 E.$$

The third of the 2-geon tensor base states,

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \mapsto (-{}^1i\sigma_2)(1)E = -{}^1i\sigma_2 E \quad (4)$$

The fourth of the 2-geon tensor base states,

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \mapsto (-{}^1i\sigma_2)(-{}^2i\sigma_2)E = {}^1i\sigma_2 {}^2i\sigma_2 E.$$

Admittedly, visually the column matrix rendition looks more appealing and "physical" but that's a bit of a mirage. What we are going to see later is that the geometric algebra 2-geon states are superior for deriving basic results like the Pauli Exclusion principle. For that though, we need to get an expression for the singlet 2-geon state.

The singlet state The isotropic spin-coupled singlet state,

$$|\varpi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|+-\rangle - |-+\rangle)$$

is expressed in geometric algebra of Cl_3^+ two-geon space as,

$$\varpi = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} ({}^1i\sigma_2 - {}^2i\sigma_2) E.$$

Using the previous tensor base states we've got a sum of two of them, from (3) and (4):

$$\begin{aligned} |\varpi\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|+-\rangle - |-+\rangle) \\ &\mapsto \varpi = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} ((-{}^2i\sigma_2) - (-{}^1i\sigma_2)) E \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} ({}^1i\sigma_2 - {}^2i\sigma_2) E \end{aligned}$$

as required.

ϖ can be factored into two new idempotents, as follows:

$$\varpi = \frac{1}{2} (1 + {}^1i\sigma_2 {}^2i\sigma_2) \frac{1}{2} (1 + {}^1i\sigma_3 {}^2i\sigma_3) \sqrt{2} {}^1i\sigma_2$$

The quantum scalar product, translated to Cl_3^+ ,

$$\langle \psi | \phi \rangle \longleftrightarrow \langle \tilde{\psi} \phi \rangle - \langle \tilde{\psi} \phi i \sigma_3 \rangle i \sigma_3$$

shows the singlet state ϖ is already unit normalized.

This spinor conventionally encodes a lot of the mystery of quantum mechanics. And yet, all we've got is that it is,

- spin-coupled,

⁶ These are still topological 4-geons, here "2-4geon" refers to the Fock space of a pair of coupled fermions.

- rotationally covariant,
- represents a wormhole bridge between the one-geons (in T4G Context).

and if that third point is taken seriously that's the only non-classical thing about the singlet state ϖ . It's all classical spacetime geometry otherwise, with the weird thing being how we interpret this object, a spacetime Pauli spinor, as an instruction for telling us what will happen if we measure the spin orientations at each of the possibly spacelike separated locations $\{\mathbb{1}\gamma_\mu\}$ and $\{\mathbb{2}\gamma_\mu\}$.

The thing that existing T4G theory cannot yet show is why an ER-bridge couples the spins in a singlet state and not in one of the other paired states. On the other hand, this could be taken as a sort of definition of what an ER=EPR bridge accomplishes. Then T4G theory would be about figuring out why that is, and what sort of properties the putative EPR wormhole has to have.

We need to show ϖ is rotationally covariant.

II.B.4. The singlet state is rotationally covariant

What we need is a joint rotor to perform the rotation, plus the knowledge from the Pauli algebra that under a rotation a spinor transforms by single sided left-multiplication (recall all pure k -blades would transform double-sided).

The rotor's carry the labels for the separate copies of the frames, so we've got a rotor:

$$R = \mathbb{1}R \mathbb{2}R$$

and to rotate the singlet state, it is:

$$\varpi \longrightarrow \varpi' = \mathbb{1}R \mathbb{2}R \varpi$$

To simplify the rotated ϖ , we show that for the singlet state,

$$\mathbb{1}i\sigma_3\varpi = -\mathbb{2}i\sigma_3\varpi$$

and hence that also,

$$\mathbb{1}i\sigma_1\varpi = -\mathbb{2}i\sigma_1\varpi$$

and hence, finally, that for *any* even multivector M , in the Pauli algebra \mathcal{Cl}_3^+ ,

$$\mathbb{1}M\varpi = \mathbb{2}M^\dagger\varpi. \quad (5)$$

We now use this result to show that the singlet state ϖ is rotationally covariant.

We know rotors satisfy,

$$R\tilde{R} = 1$$

so since the Hermitian conjugate is in timespace signature, $M^\dagger = -\gamma_0\tilde{M}\gamma_0$, and if M is even grade then it commutes with γ_0 , so we get,

$$M^\dagger = \tilde{M}, \quad \text{for } M \text{ even.}$$

The rotors are even elements of \mathcal{Cl}_3^+ , so we can directly apply (5), and the hint above,

$$\varpi' = \mathbb{1}R \mathbb{2}R \varpi = \mathbb{1}R \mathbb{1}R^\dagger \varpi = \varpi.$$

We could have proven this using the general rotation matrix, but the use of rotors for rotation is more elegant, so worth demonstrating, and also keeps us in the one algebra. The cost (of this elegance) was having to prove the lemma above for the even multivectors.

Anyway, now we've found spin coupling, rotational covariance, hence ISC states, and all with classical geometry and the only weird bit of it being how to interpret the coupling, and from T4G we're claiming it's via an ER=EPR bridge.

It is possible now to state the Pauli Exclusion Principle in this language.

II.C. The Pauli Principle

In the *STA and electron physics* paper [3], Doran *et al* develop the wave equations for the multi-particle systems at this stage. We are going to skip that because it's not essential for the rest of this paper.

All we need to know is that in a simple (non-relativistic, elastic scattering) measurement theory the Pauli spinors describe well enough what the results of measurements of the two-particle system will be, and that if the two geons are coupled then the spin measurements will be more correlated than classical mechanics can account for, they will be Bell correlated.

The previous expressions using the quantum correlator showed us how to describe such correlations. We are interpreting them as an implied ER=EPR bridge connection, such that the pair of particles share two horizons and the same qubits. Enough qubits to describe two particles, not just one.

So we could say this is "not quite" a minimal Planck wormhole, but it's the next most minimal ER bridge. And as O'Hara's results [4] already alerted us to: hardly a more minimal wormhole is possible, since entanglements involving more wormholes would have to violate rotational covariance, and so would be *distinguishable* particles.

The trouble was, O'Hara's formalism for all this exploited existing Dirac bra-ket machinery, which obscures the *real* geometry. So now we wish to see how it is all described with real geometric algebra. And we've already obtained the singlet state for a spin $\uparrow \downarrow$ coupled system.

II.C.1. What is the Pauli Principle?

You can (for the moment) forget about the field commutation relations, there're not fundamental, since the field variables are fictional accounting tools useful for differential Hamiltonian time evolution. We want to be doing T4G theory, which is global and must deal with a

full 4D cobordism all at once, and that means — if we do not want to risk madness — simplifying analysis to the spacetime boundaries of a measurement process.

At the measurement boundaries what matters are the symmetry principles, since they express what is conserved. (Deep down that’s all the field variable commutators were expressing as well.)

But at this level of analysis this means the Pauli Exclusion Principle boils down to a simple statement about symmetry of the wave functions or spinors used to describe possible outcomes of spin measurements. (Implying a magnetic field of some sort or another, possibly Stern-Gerlach, or more naturally the Coulomb fields of an atomic nucleus. Anything that can be counted as a type of detection of the geon’s spin.) The statement is, for a wave packet $\psi = \underline{1}\psi$ describing two-geons,

$$\psi(\vec{r}) = -\psi(\mathcal{I}[\vec{r}]).$$

where \vec{r} is an 8-dimensional coordinate vector, and

$$\vec{r} = \underline{1}q + \underline{2}s$$

is the multi-particle 3-space position tensor, and \mathcal{I} is abstractly the operation (we know not yet how to do it) of “swapping the particles,” that is, abstractly,

$$\mathcal{I}[\underline{1}q + \underline{2}s] = \underline{1}s + \underline{2}q$$

It is worth staring at that for a minute. The English symbols q and s are standing for Euclidean vectors ($x = q_1, y = q_2, z = q_3$), and ($x = s_1, y = s_2, z = s_3$), while the left underbar scripts stand for the separate copies of the spacetime frames, i.e., particle labels. So the abstract operator \mathcal{I} really is “swapping geons.”

The point of the Pauli Principle is that when the particles are indistinguishable, we should see no essential physics change if we swap them around, and yet if we make some physical swap (via say wormhole traversals) something does change, a sign on the two-geon wave function. This sign change has no effect classically, due to employment of Kolmogorov probabilities, but quantum mechanically it is a phase change on the measurement algebra descriptors (the spinor tensor) and can lead to interference effects, and that’s what “causes” the Pauli exclusion phenomenon. It’s an interference phenomenon.

In T4G terms, it is an effect of wormhole topology, which is the underlying cause of all the non-classical interference effects.

To do this in \mathcal{Cl}_3^+ we first seek a multivector operator (so just a multivector) that swaps (x, y, z) coordinates on a spinor like the singlet state ϖ , but which does so for *both* of the tensor subspaces simultaneously, so it has to invert or swap a frame $\{\underline{1}\gamma_\mu\}$ with a frame $\{\underline{2}\gamma_\mu\}$.

But we cannot simply parity swap the coordinates in the geometric algebra C_{3*+} treatment, because recall the two-geon spinor $\underline{1}\psi$ was a little more complicated than a 1-4geon spinor, since it has two copies of the spacetime algebra. It’s a tensor product space object.

So we need a frame swapping multivector operation, and there isn’t one single multivector geometric product to do this (at least we think not, you could try finding one). But there is a next best thing, which is a single multivector that can perform the frame swapping by a double-sided geometric product, so just like the action of a rotor for rotations.

II.C.2. The geon exchange operation \mathcal{I} , in GA

Fortunately we did not need to figure out any of this ourselves, Doran *et al* [3] found it for us. All we need to do is verify that it works. It is denoted \mathcal{I} (think of it as “frame inversion”), but it is really a swap, not an invert, and is defined by,

$$\mathcal{I} = \Gamma_0\Gamma_1\Gamma_2\Gamma_3$$

where,

$$\Gamma_\mu = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(\underline{1}\gamma_\mu + \underline{2}\gamma_\mu).$$

Checking this works can be now made into exercises. We can show that,

$$\mathcal{I}^2 = -1.$$

this is what we’d expect if we think we need to act double-sided by \mathcal{I} to do a coordinate frame swap.

We can then show that \mathcal{I} does indeed invert coordinates in each tensor subspace correctly, that is,

$$\mathcal{I}\underline{1}\gamma_\mu\mathcal{I} = \underline{2}\gamma_\mu, \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{I}\underline{2}\gamma_\mu\mathcal{I} = \underline{1}\gamma_\mu.$$

In other words, \mathcal{I} is confirmed as the particle-exchange operation in the geometric algebra \mathcal{Cl}_3^+ . It is trivial now to show that,

$$\mathcal{I}(\langle q1 \rangle + \langle s2 \rangle)\mathcal{I} = \underline{1}s + \underline{2}q$$

all you need to do is note $\underline{1}q = \underline{1}\gamma_\mu q^\mu$ and $\underline{2}s = \underline{2}\gamma_\mu s^\mu$, for $\mu \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$.

II.C.3. Geon exchange is rotationally covariant

Recall the Pauli Principle, or ISC statistics, applies only to pairs of geons, and in particular we get Fermi-Dirac statistics for the singlet state ϖ . We are cheating here because we know this from orthodox QM. Nevertheless, for geometric algebra pedagogy we can imagine some genius figuring this out using the GA language rather than Dirac bra-kets.

The question to hand is how do we know the geon exchange $\mathcal{I}\psi\mathcal{I}$ will preserve rotational covariance?

We should also worry about preserving solutions to the Dirac equation, since we’d like the geon-exchanged two-geon system to be a solution to the Dirac equation, otherwise it will not be counted as “behaving like a fermion”.

You might think this is trivial, since "How can swapping the coordinate frames possibly change solutions to the wave equations?" You'd be right, but we have no right to just assume this. So we also have to show the exchanged state is a symmetry of the Dirac equation for paired geons.

These are the two next tasks: check $\mathcal{I}\psi\mathcal{I}$ is;

- (i) rotationally covariant,
- (ii) Lorentz invariant,
- (iii) a symmetry of Dirac 2-geon equation.

a. Rotational covariance. The problem to solve is to show that if we rotate the tensored frames $\{\mathbb{1}\gamma_\mu\}$ and $\{\mathbb{2}\gamma_\mu\}$ equally, then we should paranoid-like in a worst case scenario expect to get a different geon-exchange operator \mathcal{I}' , which would be a bad thing because it would mean \mathcal{I} would depend upon our choice of spacetime frames, and we actually want it not to! We would like to find a 2-geon exchange operator that does *not* depend upon our choice of frame!

we rotate the frame basis vectors nothing happens to the new \mathcal{I}' it should end up equal to the original \mathcal{I} . So let's see if the good scenario is always going to be true.

We rotate frame vectors as normal in GA with a rotor,

$$\mathbb{1}\gamma'_\mu = \mathbb{1}R(\mathbb{1}\gamma_\mu)\mathbb{1}\tilde{R}$$

and similarly for the other tensor subspace, with a rotor $\mathbb{2}R$. This will change the Γ_μ in the definition of \mathcal{I} , and that will completely describe or new \mathcal{I}' by definition. For the Γ we've got,

$$\Gamma'_\mu = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\mathbb{1}R(\mathbb{1}\gamma_\mu)\mathbb{1}\tilde{R} + \mathbb{2}R(\mathbb{2}\gamma_\mu)\mathbb{2}\tilde{R} \right)$$

but the slickness of our notation means we can gather the rotors to the left and right hand sides, since each labelled rotor acts only on its labelled tensor subspace, hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma'_\mu &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \mathbb{1}R \mathbb{2}R (\mathbb{1}\gamma_\mu + \mathbb{2}\gamma_\mu) \mathbb{2}\tilde{R} \mathbb{1}\tilde{R} \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \mathbb{1}R \mathbb{2}R \Gamma_\mu \mathbb{2}\tilde{R} \mathbb{1}\tilde{R} \end{aligned}$$

We have to use this to define the new \mathcal{I} , which is the geometric product of all these, which is thus,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{I}' &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \mathbb{1}R \mathbb{2}R \Gamma_0 \mathbb{2}\tilde{R} \mathbb{1}\tilde{R} \mathbb{1}R \mathbb{2}R \Gamma_1 \mathbb{2}\tilde{R} \mathbb{1}\tilde{R} \\ &\quad \dots \mathbb{1}R \mathbb{2}R \Gamma_3 \mathbb{2}\tilde{R} \mathbb{1}\tilde{R} \end{aligned}$$

Now notice all the inner rotors cancel in pairs, since $R\tilde{R} = 1$ for any individual rotor whatsoever. So this is cleans up to,

$$\mathcal{I}' = \mathbb{1}R \mathbb{2}R \mathcal{I} \mathbb{2}\tilde{R} \mathbb{1}\tilde{R}$$

To finish the demonstration we need to consider what this "new" \mathcal{I}' does to even elements in $\mathcal{C}\ell_3^+$. For scalars it is obvious, since they just "move through" all the rotors, and that will leave us with $\mathcal{I}^2 = -1$.

For other even elements we've only got bivectors like $a \wedge b$ in each subspace. But consider how the original \mathcal{I} acts double-sided on any bivector in the single geon subspace,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{I} \mathbb{1}a \wedge \mathbb{1}b \mathcal{I} &= -\mathcal{I} \mathbb{1}a \mathcal{I} \wedge \mathcal{I} \mathbb{1}b \mathcal{I} \\ &= -\mathbb{2}b \wedge \mathbb{2}a \end{aligned}$$

where on the second line there we just inserted a pair \mathcal{I}^2 which is illegally inserting a -1 , hence the prefactor -1 out front to cancel this.

In other words, the effect of sandwiching a bivector between $\mathcal{I}(\dots)\mathcal{I}$ is to exchange the tensor spaces but with a sign change too. The bivector gets flipped a sign upon particle exchange. There is no such change for a vector or odd grade element of the algebra, they just get exchanged without a sign change, since the γ_μ do.

So think about this. Rotors have only even grade terms. This means we can, by using the same trick of inserting a few \mathcal{I}^2 , write,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{I} \mathbb{1}\tilde{R} \mathbb{2}\tilde{R} &= -\mathcal{I} \mathbb{1}\tilde{R} \mathcal{I} \mathcal{I} \mathbb{2}\tilde{R} \\ &= +\mathbb{2}\tilde{R} \mathcal{I} \mathbb{2}\tilde{R} \\ &= -\mathbb{2}\tilde{R} \mathcal{I} \mathbb{2}\tilde{R} \mathcal{I} \mathcal{I} \\ &= +\mathbb{2}\tilde{R} \mathbb{1}\tilde{R} \mathcal{I} \end{aligned}$$

Now substitute this result for the last three factors in the above expression,

$$\mathcal{I}' = \mathbb{1}R \mathbb{2}R \mathcal{I} \mathbb{2}\tilde{R} \mathbb{1}\tilde{R}$$

and we get,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{I}' &= (\mathbb{1}R)(\mathbb{2}R)(\mathbb{2}\tilde{R})(\mathbb{1}\tilde{R})\mathcal{I} \\ &= \mathcal{I} \end{aligned}$$

which is what we hoped for, the geon-exchanger \mathcal{I} is rotationally covariant. A few parentheses to make it easier to read back there, you can see repeated applying unitarity of rotors $R\tilde{R} = 1$ vanishes them all.

b. Lorentz invariance of \mathcal{I} . Lorentz invariance is a matter of checking the action of \mathcal{I} does not change under a boost. But boosts are nothing but rotations with the timelike relative bivectors in the STA, and we've already shown the exchange operator is invariant under rotations.

If you wish to check the fine details then just look at section 9.5 in the *Spacetime algebra and electron physics* paper [3]. It is only a couple of paragraphs long, so hardly worth reproducing here.

It is slightly more interesting to run through the check that the exchanged wave-function is still a solution to the Dirac Equation for the two-geon system, because this requirement does not automatically follow from rotational invariance. We do not wish to cover Dirac Theory, so refer to Doran *et al* Sec.9.5 in [29].

c. Summary of Pauli Exclusion. There is a lot more that could be written on the applications of Pauli exclusion and "exchange forces." In STA there are numerical

simulations for one, but we are not interested in such applied physics. Here we can just make do with summarizing what Pauli Exclusion looks like in simplest fundamental terms in the geometric algebra.

First, we find that the exchanged state,

$$\psi' = \mathcal{I} \psi(\mathcal{I}x\mathcal{I}) \mathcal{I}$$

is Lorentz invariant and a solution to the Dirac equation whenever $\psi(x)$ is a solution.

Second, this being the case we know the fully antisymmetrized wave function, denoted $\psi_{\mathcal{I}}$,

$$\psi_{\mathcal{I}} = \psi(x) + \mathcal{I} \psi(\mathcal{I}x\mathcal{I}) \mathcal{I}$$

thus also solves the Dirac equation, but also is by construction invariant under the exchange operator,

$$\psi_{\mathcal{I}} = \mathcal{I} \psi_{\mathcal{I}}(\mathcal{I} \times \mathcal{I}) \mathcal{I}$$

This last expression is the full and complete statement of Pauli Exclusion in the spacetime Pauli algebra. All the practical effects of Pauli Exclusion follow therefrom.

What orthodox QM and QFT cannot and do not supply, we have available now a realist underpinning for Pauli exclusion, which is that the effect follows from pairwise coupling in a rotationally covariant “state” — which in orthodox QM and QFT is nothing but a mathematical formalism, hence quite mystical. In T4G theory we have a realist *picture of this mathematics*, which is that an ER=EPR bridge connects the pairs in these Bell states, and so entanglement, *à la* Paul O’Hara, is responsible for Pauli Exclusion. O’Hara almost had this, but did not posit the ER bridge as the geometric causal factor.

The singlet state we denoted ϖ in the last chapter, is the Measurement Theory description of a minimal Maldacena-Susskind wormhole topology. We call it a “quantum state” but in fact it is pure gravity. Non-classical *classical* gravity mind you.

This statement or claim might make more sense if you think of QM as just a model of measurement processes. The key is the “quantum state” or “wave-function” needs to be interpreted as instructions for what can happen (what we need to do to a lab reference frame) *when we conduct measurements*. The “state” is not the elementary particle. The “quantum state” is physically more like a process, not an object.

II.D. PEP Beyond Just the Math

In the previous section the spin–statistics follows as a pure mathematics result, albeit with physical interpretation. There is still a residual mystery, namely why on earth are spinors adequate models for the transformations among the Clifford frames? And why are the actual physical elementary particles accounted for by these spinors? What is the physical–geometry basis for this model adequacy, if indeed it is physical–geometry?

It is very difficult to dream up a definitive account without *presupposing* some ontology.

If we presuppose T4G ontology then the phenomena become reasonably comprehensible. Our solution is that there is no reason why a classical spacetime topological geon should be constrained by Fermi-Dirac statistics. But if we couple 4-geons in a rotationally invariant state, then the ER-bridge connecting them *physically* is modelled effectively in the quantum theory by the *algebraic* C-bridge, or EPR-bridge in the specific case of Bell pairs.

An algebraic C-bridge is implicit in the structure of the elementary particles. This is also a coupling principle. This is essentially why there can be no classical 4-geons. Any C-bridge coupling in T4G theory is basically equivalent (functorially, one may say) to physical ER-bridge coupling, which is entanglement, which is strictly non-classical.

II.E. Paramagnetism and Superconductors

O’Hara discusses these two phenomena [5], pointing out that the distinguishing feature of the Pauli exclusion effect is not spin-1/2, but the spin-coupling. From that paper,

“From the perspective of this article [*Ibid.*], this gives rise to the ambivalent situation of referring to particles as fermions, although they are no longer subjected to the Pauli exclusion principle. With our approach, this ambiguity is removed and a more natural and coherent explanation of the transition from Fermi-Dirac to Boltzmann statistics is forthcoming. Essentially, the Boltzmann statistics emerge when the spin coupling which seems to be the underlying cause of the Fermi-Dirac statistics is first broken and the particles then move apart to become distinguishable and statistically independent. This breaking of the coupling occurs naturally when the temperature is raised, and they become distinguishable and independent when the distance separating the particles becomes large enough to overcome interactions between the particles. As a result, the particles obey Boltzmann statistics . . .”

This is a nice account, with useful practical examples. It still leaves the spacetime physics of the coupling unaccounted for, and we think T4G theory offers an account which fills in this explanatory gap.

Why would high temperature break the coupling? Why would interaction re-couple (re-entangle)? The only mechanism we can reasonably suppose is that this coupling (or specific form of entanglement) is spacetime mediated, and so high energy collisions break the ER-bridge structure. Due to vacuum entanglement this will reform elsewhere, for topological invariant reasons, but the point

is the fermions (or now bosons, in EPRB) that were coupled, are decoupled and become statistically distinguishable.

When spin-coupled why were they indistinguishable and hence subject to the statistics of Pauli (Fermi-Dirac)? The only reasonable account is that the existence of the ER-bridge means we cannot have separated the two 4-geons. They are in a very real spacetime sense, one-system. Hence indistinguishable.

We must resist here the laziness of thinking of the spinors and the particles as the same thing, they are not. The ψ are still transformation instructions, so they merely encode Pauli exclusion. The physical particles are coupled, and so are not distinguishable fermion particles until some measurement or kinetic disturbance separates them, breaking the coupling (breaking entanglement in the statistical correlation sense, but equivalently breaking the wormhole ER-bridge in the physical sense).

II.F. Bosons in Singlet States

To truly reveal the essence of Pauli Exclusion we turn again to Paul O'Hara, who pointed out [5] the photons prepared in the singlet state for Bell EPR experiments are fermionic. The bosons are fermionic when they are coupled. In these experiments we can still call this ISC — spin-coupling — owing to the experiments being of the helicity. The generalization is then obvious: when a particle is entangled then there is Pauli Exclusion at some level of description.

Normally we never talk about a single particle having a Pauli Exclusion with itself, but at least poetically you might say that failure of a particle to exhibit infinite self-energy is a type of exclusion principle, and it (again poetically) relates to the next topic of this paper.

III. VIRTUAL PARTICLES

We now turn to the second theme of the paper. The issue is *given* (1) the perturbative expansion of the path integral is mathematically legitimate, (2) it is stochastic, albeit with interference, then is there a 4D spacetime and *non-virtual* account of the internal structures most textbooks refer to as ‘virtual particles’ or ‘vacuum processes’?

III.A. Internal lines, open cobordisms, and effective nonlocal exchange

Definition 4 (Open cobordism). *By an open cobordism we mean a spacetime region specified by boundary data that is not dynamically closed under the effective degrees of freedom used to describe the experiment. In particular, the region may exchange information, correlation, or*

conserved quantities with exterior sectors through entanglement or nontrivial spacetime topology.

Proposition 5 (Why the borrowed-energy heuristic fails). *The energy–time uncertainty relation does not license violations of exact energy conservation in individual processes. It constrains statistical spreads in measurement outcomes and time scales, not temporary suspension of the dynamical conservation laws.*

Proposition 6 (Internal lines as effective traces of open-system exchange). *In a perturbative expansion of the path integral over an open cobordism, internal propagator lines need not be interpreted as particles created from the vacuum and annihilated a short time later. Rather, they encode amplitude-level contributions from intermediate processes that are not representable within a strictly local, closed-subsystem description.*

Conjecture 2 (Topological reification of the vertices but not virtual particles). *The topology-changing events depicted by Stückelberg–Feynman vertices correspond to real processes occurring in the open cobordism, mediated by wormhole or entanglement structure, such that conservation laws are maintained globally and locally, even when the local effective description in a Minkowski frame (trivial topology) makes the process **appear** off-shell.*

The point of this conjecture is to provide an alternative to the orthodox accounts of SOH which sweep under the rug the conceptual problems of off-shell processes. The T4G conjecture is that there really are no off-shell processes *per se*, but if one treats the system as closed and isolated, ignoring the Planck scale topology, then the only account one probably *could* provide would be of something akin to off-shell virtual particles.

The difficulty, in our opinion, with the older *orthodox* QFT accounts is that they reify the fields. We do not, but we do reify the topology changing processes. The philosophical question is which is the more parsimonious? The physics question is: can the distinction be tested, and how?

With old orthodox QFT one must regard the spinor fields as ontological, and as being surplus structure to 4D spacetime, and with the fantastical properties of these vacuum fluctuations, or “borrowed energy.” We have shown there is a more parsimonious alternative spacetime account that conservatively retains the Clifford algebra understanding[11], and the ISQM view [7], that the spinor fields are not real, and are stochastic descriptors of transformation of the more physical but underlying degrees of freedom.

What our conjectures have to give up is the idea the isolated QM system is a closed and isolated system. Our view is that it is precisely because all spacetime cobordism are open systems that the weird and fantastical vacuum effects appear to occur, but which *appear* weird and fantastical only because one is presuming the system is closed, when in fact it is open.

This may also be framed as a separation of scales issue: if one could literally see and inspect spacetime entanglement structure, no one would be thinking of an “isolated particle” as a closed system, and they’d not say it was isolated. Isolated systems would then have a meaning only at a much higher level of description, specifically about 10^{15} orders of magnitude in length or time above the entanglement scale. (In T4G theory the entanglement scale is basically the Planck scale⁷.)

We should note this new interpretation is not necessarily unique to T4G theory. All we wish to note is that an alternative ontological reading is *possible*: perturbation theory is tracking genuine but non-locally completed processes. One test of this view, in principle, would be highly sensitive measurement of exact conservation laws. In our T4G view, there is no need to say the conservation laws are respected only *on average* for some divine reason, they would be respected absolutely (for divine reason, you may argue). One must however make extraordinarily sensitive measurements to check this hypothesis.

III.B. Interference from entanglement

We will suppress the temptation to also discuss in depth how entanglement provides an adequate account for all quantum interference phenomena, which will be the subject of further research, but it may be of interest to readers to note Paul O’Hara has already written about this [6]. O’Hara’s conceptualization is however specific to the Two Slit experiment.

We can offer a more general conceptualization by appealing to a notion of wormhole pinning. Nothing previous in this paper depends upon this being real physics, it is just an interesting observation, providing a realist account of both EPR and Two Slit interference. The issue of Kochen–Specker Contextuality will be addressed hopefully in future papers.

III.B.1. Two Slit Experiment Amplitudes

Probably the simplest way to conduct a mathematical formal analysis of Young’s experiment with *single photons* is the path integral formulation of Feynman. This avoids the fictional account of some sort of physical wave interference, which Schrödinger long ago pointed out was absurd (the “wave” in Hilbert space is not in physical space).

Schrödinger position was subtler than the popular textbook story. Although he initially pursued a literal

wave-mechanical account, he later understood the many-body wavefunction is generally defined on configuration space rather than ordinary physical space, and in his later writings he described the quantum state as an “expectation catalog” rather than a directly material wave.⁸

The core of the T4G account of the Two Slit experiment is not the sum-over-histories. The core is the simple ER-bridge entanglement. This is O’Hara’s lesson: Pauli exclusion and interference for singlet states is more fundamentally a coupling principle, not a superposition principle.

The reason superposition comes into play at a first or zeroth order level in the Two Slit experiment is really only because the singlet state ϖ is described in the mathematical formalism by a superposition. In T4G theory we recognize it not as a superposition, but as a wormhole bridge. The geon really is in two places at any time, but when detected the ER-bridge must collapse and so it is no longer in two places, at least not for a split second or femtosecond or whatever — until it gets entangled with bits of the measurement apparatus and then thus spread out again.

a. Caveats. We want to point out another of Paul O’Hara’s papers, this one is on the *EPR Paradox and SU(2) symmetry* [33] — in it O’Hara almost gets around to using geometric algebra, as we’ve done in this chapter, but he failed to release himself from the grip of the matrix representation of the Pauli algebra.

At the end of his paper O’Hara rediscovers the result of Hestenes, Lasenby and Doran, *et al.*, which is that the bivector which encodes the instruction to rotate is a component factor of the Pauli spinor ψ , and further, that it is the invariance of the coupled two-4geon bivector under $SL(2, \mathbb{C})$ which is responsible for EPR correlation. In addition the spin vector property of the particle (geon) described by the instruction ψ , is $SU(2)$ frame-of-reference dependent. Finally O’Hara suggests multipartite entanglement seen in GHZ states is an analogous consequence of a more general invariance under a semigroup, denoted $SM(2, \mathbb{C})$.

O’Hara somewhat mystically writes this as an expression that, “the whole is more than the sum of its parts,” but T4G provides a non-mystical account for that, which is that an ER bridge connects the “parts” of every “elementary particle.” So the deep principle rediscovered here is only that elementary particles are; (a) not point-like, and (b) are not trivially embedded in spacetime like superstrings or p -branes, but are rather non-trivially connected, via wormhole topologies.

What we would further suggest is that with the aid of the geometric algebra approach we are probably well

⁷ The topology for entanglement, the Planck scale ER-bridges are Planckian, but of course two ends of a wormhole can be arbitrarily far apart in spacetime. This accounts for why quantum effects seem to mix these vastly separate scales.

⁸ See Schrödinger, *Collected Papers on Wave Mechanics* [30]; and Schrödinger, *The Present Status of Quantum Mechanics* [31], where the language of an “expectation-catalog” is explicit. For historical discussion which is counter-point to our single universe realist views, see Allori *et al.*, *Many-Worlds and Schrödinger’s First Quantum Theory* [32].

situated to account for GHZ states within the geometry of spacetime rotors.

Our own attitude to this project is that it'd be nice to complete, but we feel it is more applied physics than fundamental physics, so we have to leave it to brighter people to polish off.

A more general account of all quantum interference based on entanglement is still a topic of on-going research. The basic idea is similar to O'Hara's Two Slit interference account, but differs in generality. O'Hara's account is basically operational. He uses spin coupling. A more generic account for interference based on entanglement is that of T4G theory, where ER-bridge structure accounts for entanglement correlations and whereby oscillations across these ER-bridges give rise to all interference. This offers the possibility that we can get the interference in the T4G cobordism we need to complete our conjectures above.

This stated, note that there is a purely logical argument due to Barandes [7] that if there is entanglement (spacetime indivisibility) then *there will be interference*, exactly as prescribed in orthodox quantum mechanics without any deep understanding of why. The T4G theory could be a good explanation for the *why*, or the *how*.

III.B.2. Note on Alternatives.

This idea that the generic spacetime cobordism is an open system, but in the subtle way that only vacuum scale wormholes can connect the interior to the light cone envelope exterior, is only the main mechanism we propose for previously denoted 'virtual processes.' An alternative we consider also possible is spacetime topology fluctuation. How might this occur without the mysticism of QFT?

We do not know of a good answer. But since in GR spacetime is dynamical, nothing explicitly prevents spontaneous topology change in the vacuum — given that enough energy density may randomly accumulate in a small neighbourhood to excite a topology change. This is Wheeler's spacetime foam model. In our present context we would be seeking theoretical justification for such fluctuations without appealing to the mysticism of fields modes. The spacetime metric, in T4G theory, being the same ontology as in Einstein–Hilbert gravity, but with non-trivial topology, so that locally in any given tiny Planck-volume neighbourhood spacetime is still smooth and Minkowski, but on the scale of an elementary particle Minkowski topology breaks down, and gets recovered again only at a much larger scale where effects of entanglement become again negligible.

We have not reviewed current state-of-the-art spacetime foam theory [34–36]. The contribution we suggest is fairly minor, and would be that smaller than a Planck volume the spacetime foam should break down due to gravitational singularity formation, or the model we presently prefer: CPT-mirror boundary formation

[37] in Planck sized regions. This would be regarded as a kind of topological censorship, or in this particular case, spacetime foam all-the-way-down censorship.

IV. DISCUSSION

While it is not necessary to “unify” Pauli Exclusion and virtual particle processes, we could summarize this present paper in philosophical terms with a mini conjecture:

Conjecture 3 (Unified topological origin of exclusion and interference). *Both antisymmetric exchange in isotropically spin-coupled fermionic systems and the interference structure associated with perturbative internal lines are cobordism boundary manifestations of an underlying open-cobordism dynamics with non-trivial entanglement topology.*

This is only a mini-conjecture, the greater conjecture would be the main project of T4G theory, which is that all fundamental physics can be accounted for with non-trivial spacetime topology, as originally conceived of by Hadley [17, 18].

This said, our wider philosophical position is that Schrödinger may have been more correct than he realized, and almost all non-classical phenomena in our universe derive from entanglement. The critical point we would like to emphasize is that entanglement is subtle, and has not only (i) Bell pair manifestations, but also (ii) vacuum and (iii) particle self-entanglement manifestations.

This is a broad claim, motivated by our topological 4-geon model explorations, but it could apply to several alternative ontologies for QM.

IV.A. \mathbb{C} -analytic structure

This topic belongs in the discussion because it is both more speculative and more general than the results established earlier in the paper. The issue is where the complex structure should live if one insists on a genuinely spacetime-based account.

In ordinary geometric quantum mechanics, the natural Kähler structure belongs not to physical spacetime itself, but to the quantum state space, namely the projective Hilbert space of pure states. The latter carries a compatible complex structure, symplectic form, and metric. Our question is therefore not whether Lorentzian spacetime is already Kähler in the orthodox sense; in general it is not. The question is whether a spacetime formulation based on open cobordisms and entanglement topology can generate an effective state space or moduli space with the analogous complex-symplectic-metric structure.

From the standpoint of spacetime algebra this is a non-trivial issue. The STA contains several distinguished elements squaring to -1 , including timelike directions, bivector generators of rotations, and the pseudoscalar.

But these are not scalars, and they already possess definite spacetime-geometric interpretations. For that reason they do not, by themselves, explain the strictly scalar and globally coherent complex phase structure of quantum mechanics. At best they show that local pseudo-complex structures are abundant in spacetime geometry; they do not yet explain why quantum amplitudes exhibit a genuinely holomorphic organization.

Our proposal is therefore conditional and programmatic. If quantum mechanics is to be reformulated as a stochastic theory of open spacetime cobordisms, then the relevant mathematical object is not bare Lorentzian spacetime but the space of admissible boundary data, histories, or effective cobordism sectors. It is on that space that one should seek a compatible complex structure, symplectic form, and metric – that is, a Kähler structure, or in the indefinite case a pseudo-Kähler structure. In this sense the complex analyticity of quantum theory would arise not from local spacetime alone, but from the geometry of the stochastic cobordism state space.

We do not yet have a precise theorem proving that wormhole topology supplies such a structure. What wormhole topology may supply is the necessary non-local connectivity from which a complex phase geometry on the cobordism state space can emerge. Our conjecture is that vacuum entanglement and Planck-scale wormhole structure furnish precisely the missing ingredient needed to lift local pseudo-complex structures of STA into the global complex geometry characteristic of quantum amplitudes.

Our proposal is that the strictly \mathbb{C} -holomorphic structure in QM is all due to the spacetime wormhole topology of the associated T4G theory, or something like T4G. This is a *projective functor* relationship: the \mathbb{C} -analytic structure is in the stochastic transformation category, not the spacetime cobordism category (which remains real and Lorentzian). We do not yet have a theorem–proof for this, but there is a lot of evidence pointing towards this thesis being viable. We now enumerate a few of these.

1. Non-hermitian Hamiltonians (NHH’s) can have real eigenvalues provide PT symmetry holds. NHH’s are associated with classical observables taking on \mathbb{C} -values. Bender has likened some such phenomena to virtual wormholes [38].
2. Tunnelling is associated with classical observables (momentum) taking on \mathbb{C} -values [13, 14]. This was also noted by Bender [38].
3. Adopting 4D spacetime Minimalism there is no other option but that non-trivial spacetime topology is the reason QM reveals an intrinsic irremovable \mathbb{C} -analytic structure in the stochastic dynamics whenever entanglement has to be accounted for (as in *always* in the path-integral).

4. Black Hole Mirrors — this is a two-part piece of evidence:

- (a) The orthodox textbook “solutions” for black holes (and the big bang) violate causal principles at the singularities [39], and so are invalid. To recover analytic solutions, valid for all times, a CPT-mirror boundary seems to be the best alternative proposed so far [19, 37, 40], requiring re-writing of those textbooks. The physics of the CPT-mirror boundaries strongly mimics that of particle–antiparticle pair processes of the Stückelberg–Feynman diagrams. But in 4D spacetime only wormholes can account for these off-shell topological transformations.
- (b) A roughly equivalent account of these CPT mirror boundaries for black holes is from Hawking’s original QFT analysis [41, 42], which is that tunnelling is what allows Hawking radiation to escape from the black hole horizon. This involves the \mathbb{C} -observables as outlined by Bender, in point 1.

While Bender’s wormholes are merely algebraic, so are those associated with virtual processes, black hole CPT-mirror boundaries, big bang analyticity and Stückelberg–Feynman diagrams. They are all algebraic.

Our contention is that this is merely due to the fact quantum mechanics is formulated explicitly as a stochastic dynamics theory, not a geometric theory. The underlying spacetime geometry reason for all the above phenomena is not an algebraic wormhole, but an actual Planck scale wormhole bridge.

IV.B. Outlook for topological 4-geon theory

The idea much of quantum mechanics could be accounted for by assuming spacetime has non-trivial topology at the smallest scale is much more than a vague *space-time foam* hypothesis. The original idea of Hadley was that the elementary particle structure is such non-trivial topology [18, 43, 44]. Unfortunately, this rich idea has been left impoverished and seems to have skipped an entire generation of physicists. In QFT the algebra has dominated too much over geometry, and a better appreciation of the role of the spinor in QM reveals why. The spinor is a stochastic transformation instruction, not a direct element of spacetime reality.

Our paper has only skimmed the surface of two aspects of T4G theory that shed light on previously mysterious phenomena. It would be shocking if more insights and interesting experimental proposals could *not be gained* from this old but new perspective.

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